

Experiments on Resolution of Co-ordinated Inorganic Compounds into Optical Isomers. Co-ordinated Cadmium Compounds with Racemic and Active Propylenediamine.

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In continuation of our work on the complex triethylenediamine salts of cadmium (Neogi and Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 225) stable complex tripropylene diamine salts of cadmium have now been prepared with the three varieties of propylenediamine (*d*, *l* and *r*). Attempts to resolve the racemic compounds have so far been unsuccessful.

Regarding the complex compounds of cadmium with *d*- and *l*-propylenediamine, *l*-propylenediamine gave *l*-compounds and *d*-propylenediamine gave *d*-compounds, and the properties are similar to those of the racemic varieties. Tschugaeff and Sokoloff (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 3461; *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 55), however, obtained Pt, Pd and Ni compounds with opposite rotations with the two varieties of active propylenediamine. They themselves offered no explanation excepting the possibility of compounds with ring structure. It is, however, just possible that something in the nature of Walden inversion might have taken place.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Chloride was obtained by adding propylenediamine (10 g.) in small quantities to a well-cooled solution of cadmium chloride (8 g.) in water (10 g.). The clear solution deposited crystals on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. It crystallised from alcohol as white crystals, which are very soluble in water. [Found : N, 20.6; Cd, 27.6. (Cd pn₃) Cl₂ requires N, 20.71; Cd 27.74 per cent].

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Bromide was precipitated from a concentrated solution of cadmium tripropylenediamine chloride, by adding a solution of potassium bromide. It crystallised from alcohol as white crystals. It is less soluble in water than the chloride. [Found : N, 16.85; Cd 22.53. (Cd pn₃) Br₂ requires N, 16.98; Cd, 22.75 per cent].

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Iodide was precipitated by adding a saturated solution of potassium iodide to a concentrated solution of cadmium tripropylenediamine chloride. It crystallised from alcohol as white crystals soluble in acetone. [Found : N, 14.10; Cd, 19.06. (Cd pn₃) I₂ requires N, 14.27; Cd, 19.7 per cent].

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Thiocyanate, prepared by the action of potassium thiocyanate on the chloride, crystallised from alcohol. [Found : N, 18.45; Cd, 24.79. (Cd pn₃) (CNS)₂ requires N, 18.64; Cd, 25.0 per cent].

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Camphor Nitronate.—To a solution of cadmium tripropylenediamine chloride (5 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was added 5 g. of sodio *d*-camphor nitronate, dissolved in 20 c.c. of water and the mixture well shaken. The solution was then subjected to fractional crystallisation in vacuum. The first fraction was recrystallised from water as very light needles. [Found : N, 14.88; Cd, 14.5; H₂O, 4.7. (Cd pn₃) (C₁₀H₁₄O₃N)₂, 2H₂O requires N, 14.7; Cd, 14.75; H₂O, 4.72 per cent].

$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ of this substance in a dcm. tube with 5% solution was found to be +195°. The second fraction gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +189^\circ$ and the third gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +185^\circ$.

To a saturated solution of 3 g. of this substance, moderately dilute hydrochloric acid was added drop by drop and shaken till all the nitrocamphor had precipitated out which was filtered. To the filtrate excess of acetone was added whereby a small quantity of perfectly white tripropylenediamine cadmium chloride was precipitated which was allowed to settle. The supernatant liquid was then decanted off and the precipitate washed several times with acetone to remove all traces of the acid and any free nitrocamphor. It was then dissolved and examined in a polarimeter. The solution was found to be inactive. To a concentrated solution of the nitronate, a saturated solution of potassium bromide was added whereby the complex bromide was precipitated. After washing it first with a saturated solution of potassium bromide and then with water it was examined in a polarimeter. The solution was found to be inactive. Saturated solutions of potassium iodide and thiocyanate also precipitated the complex iodide and the thiocyanate respectively from the nitronate but these were also found to be inactive in water and acetone solutions.

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Camphor Sulphonate was obtained by adding a solution of the silver salt of *d*-camphor sulphonic acid to

a solution of 5 g. of cadmium tripropylenediamine chloride. The solution was filtered and evaporated in vacuum and fractionally crystallised, and the crystallised fractions gave a constant nitrogen content. [Found : N, 10.26; Cd, 15.21; H₂O, 1.94. (Cd pn₃) (C₁₀H₁₅O₄S)₂, H₂O requires N, 10.09; Cd, 13.5; H₂O, 2.16 per cent].

The values of $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ in a decm. tube for all these fractions were +23.5°. On acidifying a concentrated solution of any of these fractions with dilute HCl and adding excess of acetone, tripropylenediamine cadmium chloride was precipitated which was found to be inactive.

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Bromocamphor Sulphonate.—To a solution of cadmium tripropylenediamine chloride (5 g.), a solution of the silver salt of *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid was added gradually till addition of one drop more caused no further precipitate. The solution was filtered, and the filtrate evaporated in vacuum and fractionally crystallised. All these recrystallised fractions gave the same nitrogen content. [Found : N, 8.2; Cd, 10.52; H₂O, 8.6 (Cd pn₃ C₁₀H₁₄BrSO₄)₂, 5H₂O requires N, 8.04; Cd, 10.77; H₂O, 8.8 per cent].

Each of these fractions showed $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ in a decm. tube = +66°. On acidifying concentrated solutions of these fractions with dilute HCl and adding acetone in excess, the complex cadmium chloride was precipitated which was found to be inactive.

Cadmium Tripropylenediamine Tartrate.—A concentrated solution of cadmium tripropylenediamine chloride (5 g.) was triturated with 4.5 g. of silver tartrate. The residue of silver chloride was repeatedly extracted with hot water and the extract evaporated in vacuum and various fractions were thus obtained and all on recrystallisation gave a constant nitrogen content. [Found : N, 15.82; Cd, 20.7; H₂O, 10.31. (Cd pn₃) C₄H₄O₆, 3H₂O requires N, 15.66; Cd, 21.0; H₂O, 10.1 per cent.]. Each of these fractions showed $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ in a decm. tube = +27.5°. The tartrate was converted into the corresponding chloride by means of barium chloride but in each case the resulting solution was inactive.

The compounds with *d*- and *l*-propylenediamine have been prepared in the same way as the racemic compounds.

Cadmium l-Tripropylenediamine Chloride was obtained by combining *l*-propylenediamine prepared from *r*-propylenediamine (*cf.* Baumann, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1179; Tschugaeff, *ibid.*, 1907, 40, 3461; 1909,

42, 55) with cadmium chloride. Ten per cent. solution in water gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 37.5$ $[M] = -11.5$. (Found : N, 20.95; Cd, 27.45. Calc. N, 20.71; Cd, 27.74 per cent.).

Cadmium l-Tripropylenediamine Bromide was prepared as in the case of the *r*-variety. Ten per cent. solution of the bromide gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 25.8$ and $[M] = 127.5$. (Found : N, 16.90; Cd, 22.60. Calc. N, 16.98; Cd, 22.75 per cent.).

Cadmium l-Tripropylenediamine Iodide was prepared in the same way as the inactive varieties. Ten per cent. solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 26$, $[M] = 153$. (Found : N, 14.41; Cd, 18.7. Calc. N, 14.27; Cd, 19.1 per cent.).

Cadmium l-Tripropylenediamine Thiocyanate.—10% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 23.5$. $[M] = 106$. (Found : N, 18.77; Cd, 24.78; Calc. N, 18.64; Cd, 25.0 per cent.).

Cadmium d-Tripropylenediamine Chloride, prepared from cadmium chloride and *d*-tripropylenediamine (prepared from the *r*-variety, *cf.*, Baumann, *loc. cit.*; Tschugaeff, *loc. cit.*). 10% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +26$, $[M] = 105$. (Found : N, 20.58; Cd, 27.53. Calc. N, 20.71; Cd, 27.74 per cent.).

Cadmium d-Propylenediamine Bromide.—10% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +26.5$; $[M] = +131$. (Found : N, 17.2; Cd, 22.5; Calc. N, 16.98; Cd, 22.75 per cent.).

Cadmium d-Propylenediamine Iodide.—10% solution of the iodide gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +25$; $[M] = +147$. (Found : N, 14.39; Cd, 18.82. Calc. N, 14.27; Cd, 19.1 per cent.).

Cadmium d-Propylenediamine Thiocyanate.— $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +24.7$; $[M] = +111$. (Found : N, 18.85; Cd, 25.08. Calc. N, 18.64; Cd, 25.0 per cent.).

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Received December 18, 1935.